

BUDGET DEFICIT AND ITS IMPACT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY

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Annotation: The budget deficit and the amount of public debt are the most important indicators of the state of the economy, the article deals with the concept and essence of the budget deficit and public debt. The main causes of the budget deficit and the factors that determine the state of the budget are considered. Measures to combat the budget deficit are proposed.

Key words: budget deficit, public debt, debt obligations, budget policy, budget policy

Introduction. For the normal functioning and development of the economy, any state needs money. From which there is a need to create a fund dealing with the regulation and distribution of cash flows that are supplied to the state. This fund is called the budget. The budget is accumulated at the expense of investment income, both internal and external.

The State budget forms the central fund of monetary resources of the Government for the maintenance of the state apparatus, the armed forces, healthcare, education, and social benefits. The budget is a powerful lever of state regulation of the economy, the impact on the economic situation, the implementation of measures to stabilize it. The impact of the state on the economy occurs through financing, subsidies, transfers, etc. As a political document, the budget reflects the political and

social dynamics of society. Thanks to the budget, the State has the opportunity to focus financial resources on crucial areas of economic and social development.

Analysis of the literature used. Many foreign scientists have worked on issues related to the study of the budget deficit, in particular such as: F. Nitti, K. Amadeo, J. Eaton, M. Hertzowitz, J. Baptiste, J. Keynes, D. Ricardo, S. Tulli, etc. As well as domestic scientists D. Abdullaev, U. Burkhanov, A. Vakhobov, N. Zhumaev, I. Zhumaniyazov, T. Malikov, G. Kasimova, H. Kurbonov, M. Niezov, M. Ostonakulov, D. Rakhmonov, Z. Tozhieva, A. Sherov, etc.

Research methodology. In the process of writing the article, a set of general scientific and private methods of economic research was used: analysis and synthesis, system analysis, as well as a method of processing practical and statistical material.

The main part. The budget deficit and the amount of public debt are the most important indicators of the state of the economy, so much attention is paid to this problem. Economist F.Nitti noted that due to the growth of government spending (mostly unproductive, military), the budget deficit and public debt are increasing. Therefore, he believed that "... no matter what sacrifice it costs, but the state budget in its entirety should never end in a deficit" [2]

The state budget deficit is a condition that occurs when government expenditures exceed revenues. [5]

The factors determining the state of the budget should include (see: Fig. 1)

Fig.1 Factors determining the state of the budget (compiled by the author based on [3])

Recognizing that the budget deficit is a financial phenomenon that does not belong to the category of exceptional extraordinary events, it is nevertheless necessary to emphasize that the quality of the budget deficit itself can be different. The main reason for the budget deficit is the lag in the growth rate of budget revenues compared with the increase in budget expenditures about the causes of the budget deficit.

The following causes of its occurrence are indicated: crisis phenomena in the economy; the inability of the government to keep the financial situation in the country under control; extraordinary circumstances (wars, major natural disasters); militarization of the economy in peacetime; large centralized investments in the development of production and changing its structure; excessive increase in the growth rate of social spending compared to the growth rate of gross domestic product; increase in the cost of maintaining the administrative apparatus, etc.[3]

From the definition of the budget deficit, it follows that the main reason is the lag in revenue receipts from growing government spending. The material basis for the

formation of budget revenues at all levels is the GDP created in the process of social production, the level of budget deficit depends on fluctuations in the volume of which. The expenditure part of the budget reflects the directions of using budget revenues.

After analyzing the work, we found that, according to the results of the first nine months of 2019, the budget deficit of Uzbekistan exceeded the forecast figures by 62% and amounted to 7.3 trillion soums (\$773 million). In particular, the funds came from loans, short-term bonds and privatization of state property.

The budget deficit for 2020 is lower than planned. It was expected that the deficit in the state budget for 2020 would amount to 3.6 billion dollars (1.84 billion euros), instead of the 5.2 billion dollars (2.65 billion euros) specified in the law. According to the forecasts of the Ministry of Finance, the deficit will amount to 3% of the expected GDP. The funds are aimed at combating the consequences of the pandemic. 2.8 billion dollars (1.43 billion euro) spent on various fiscal incentives for the economy. 800 million dollars (409 million euros) were redirected from funds under various EU programs.[6]

Due to measures to combat the pandemic, government spending over the past year reached \$47.8 billion (\$24.4 billion). euro), whereas in 2019 they amounted to \$45.2 billion (23.1 billion euro).[6]

In Uzbekistan, GDP growth in 2019 amounted to 5.5%. By the end of 2020, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, despite the situation with the coronavirus, expects the country's GDP to grow by 1.5%. Similar estimates are given by international financial organizations: according to the forecasts of the World Bank, the economy of

the republic will grow by 1.6% by the end of 2020, the International Monetary Fund - by 1.8%, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development - by 1.5%. [6]

There are three traditional ways to cover the budget deficit:

- issue of state loans,
- tightening of taxation,
- money production, or "seigniorage", i.e. money printing. [7]

The budget deficit undoubtedly belongs to the so-called negative economic categories, such as inflation, crisis, unemployment, bankruptcy, which, however, are integral elements of the economic system. Moreover, without them, the economic system loses the ability to self-movement and progressive development. The budget deficit cannot be unequivocally attributed to the category of extraordinary, catastrophic events, also because the quality and nature of the deficit can be different. It may be associated with the need to make large public investments in the development of the economy, then the deficit is not a reflection of the crisis course of social processes, but rather becomes a consequence of the desire of the state to ensure progressive shifts in the structure of social reproduction.

World practice knows four main ways to solve this problem:

- reduction of budget expenditures;
- finding sources of additional income;
- the issue (issue) of unsecured money used to finance government spending;
- borrowing money from citizens, banks, business organizations, other states and foreign state organizations. [3] Such

a situation can be prevented only by carrying out a very carefully thought-out and consistent state financial policy.

The annual deficit can be covered either by the growth of public debt, or by issuing money. Even a deficit-free budget cannot indicate the health of the economy if the state has a large debt. Therefore, the analysis of the state budget deficit should be approached very carefully.

Conclusion and suggestions. A balanced budget every year is also the goal of our financial policy. But, theoretically, annual balancing reduces or completely excludes the effectiveness of the fiscal policy of the state. Thus, during periods of recession and long-term unemployment, the incomes of the population fall, therefore, tax revenues to the budget also decrease. In this case, in order to balance the budget, the state must either increase taxes or reduce government spending, which will lead to a decrease in aggregate demand.

In another case, in conditions of inflation, when monetary incomes increase, tax revenues automatically increase. To reduce revenues, the state must either reduce tax rates or increase government spending. But both of these measures or a combination of them will lead to an increase in business activity, employment and, ultimately, will not reduce inflation. It is also important to note the need for tax and structural budget reform. The main goal of improving the fiscal policy of the state should be to strengthen its stimulating function for the transition of the country's economy to the post-industrial stage of development at the beginning of the third millennium.

In the field of tax policy, the reform of the entire system of taxes and fees, the legislative basis of taxation is to be carried out. It is necessary to achieve sufficient and stable budget revenues and, if possible, to reduce tax pressure on the economy and limit its negative impact on the growth rates of production, investment and exports.

Budget expenditures should be determined by the objectives of socio-economic development. It is necessary to implement measures to strengthen control over the targeted use of public funds, to streamline the mechanism for providing various entities and for the implementation of state programs.

The public debt should be used as a tool for reviving the economy, if possible. At the same time, it is necessary to ensure an optimal ratio of long-term and short-term government obligations, as well as to use forecasted sources of servicing and repayment of public debt

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